

A Comparative Analysis of Embryo Quality and Clinical Pregnancy Following Culture of Embryos by Conventional Culture System and Uninterrupted Culture System

Sandhya Kotha

Assistant Professor, Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology, Father Colombo Institute of Medical Sciences, Warangal, Telangana State

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Corresponding Author: Dr. Sandhya Kotha

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Abstract:

Objective: The current study was done to compare the embryo quality of an uninterrupted embryo culture compared to conventional embryo culture and assessment on clinical outcomes in couples undergoing Assisted Reproductive Technology (ART). The study will compare the fertilization and cleavage rates and implantation rate between conventional culture system and uninterrupted culture.

Methods: A total of 1000 patients were included in this study who have enrolled for ART for various etiologies, among which 500 patients (Group A) belonged to conventional culture system and 500 (Group B) belonged to the uninterrupted culture system group who fulfilled the criteria were included in the study. Embryo morphology evaluation in group-A. After ICSI, injected oocytes are transferred to 4- well dish kept in groups with 1-well filled with 500µl of cleav media kept in standard bench top incubator (MINC).

Results: The study found no significant age difference between Group A (mean age 32 years) and Group B (mean age 31 years). Male factor infertility was more common in Group A, while female factor infertility was more common in Group B, though neither difference was significant. Group B showed better outcomes in embryo quality, implantation, and ongoing pregnancy rates, despite Group A having better oocyte and sperm grading. Fertilization and cleavage rates were similar, but Group B had more top-quality embryos and a significantly higher number of embryos per patient, indicating the benefits of an uninterrupted culture system.

Conclusion: This study shows that uninterrupted culture systems can enhance embryo quality, implantation efficiency and clinical pregnancy rate in ART. Consequently, these findings pose the uninterrupted culture system as a plausible candidate for enhancing ART success, which may translate into improved overall patient outcomes in fertility treatments.

Keywords: Assisted Reproductive Technology (ART), Embryo Quality, Uninterrupted Culture System, Pregnancy Rate.

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Introduction

Infertility is defined as "a disease of the reproductive system characterized by the failure to achieve a clinical pregnancy after 12 months or more of regular, unprotected sexual intercourse" [1]. Approximately 1 in 8 couples (or 12% of married women) struggle to conceive or maintain a pregnancy (NSF, CDC). Around one-third of infertility cases are attributed to the female partner, one-third to the male partner, and the remaining one-third are due to a combination of factors in both partners and are unexplained. Approximately 85-90% of infertility cases are treated with drug therapy or surgical procedures, with fewer than 3% requiring advanced reproductive technologies like In-vitro Fertilization (IVF).

The success of assisted reproductive technologies (ART) hinges on optimizing the efficiency of each step in the process. Over the past 35 years, IVF

success rates have improved significantly [2]. In ART programs, identifying the most viable embryo for transfer is crucial. However, selecting the most viable embryo from a cohort remains challenging. Clinicians primarily rely on developmental rate and morphological assessment using light microscopy as the first-line approach for embryo selection [3]. Although various non-invasive technologies for assessing human embryos have been developed, none have proven superior to standard morphological evaluation. Morphological scoring of gametes and embryos has been employed since the inception of IVF [4]. Initially, it was used to define embryo development and later as a tool for selecting the best embryos for transfer based on cell number and morphology, specifically those with the highest implantation potential. Human embryonic development follows a specifically

timed, coordinated sequence of events. Therefore, developmental rate (assessed by achieving certain milestones at specific times) and morphological characteristics (defined at particular intervals after insemination) have become the two primary morphological measures of embryonic development [5]. Various approaches have been adopted, including assessing embryos sequentially at several stages during early development or only once, immediately before transfer. Although a variety of non-invasive technologies for human embryo assessment have been developed, none have yet proven superior to standard morphological evaluation [6]. The ability to identify the most viable embryo in a cohort remains a challenge despite the numerous scoring systems currently in use. Consequently, morphological assessment has been and will likely remain the preferred method for embryo selection. In the present study, we aimed to conduct a comparative analysis of embryo quality and clinical pregnancy rates following culture in a conventional system versus uninterrupted culture in a standard trigas incubator.

Material and Methods

This retrospective cohort study was carried out at CIMAR (Center for Infertility Management and Assisted Reproduction) Cochin, Kerala, India. Institutional Ethical approval was obtained for the study as per the protocol for human research. Written consent was obtained from all the participants of the study and the confidentiality of the cases was maintained in the study.

Selection of patients: Initially small pilot study was done on 50 patients in each group, as the difference in results was noted therefore it was extended to 1000 couples.

A total of 1000 patients were included in this study who have enrolled for ART for various etiologies, among which 500 patients belonged to the conventional culture system and 500 belonged to the uninterrupted culture system group who fulfilled the criteria were included in the study. Institutional Ethics Review Board approval to analyze the embryo quality and CPR link between the conventional culture system and uninterrupted culture system and IVF outcome had been obtained.

Inclusion Criteria

1. All cases of fresh ICSI -ET cycles.

Exclusion Criteria

1. Canceled cycles due to OHSS, minimal stimulation protocol, etc.
2. Donor sperm, donor oocyte, donor embryo transfer.
3. Conventional IVF cycles.
4. Cycles where fresh ET was not performed.

However, no exclusion was made based on the type of infertility (primary and secondary), duration of infertility, coexistent female factors, and number of prior fertility treatments. Demographic characteristics of the couples were recorded. After a detailed history including sexual history, significant medical and surgical history, physical examination and local examination routine andrology work up, routine gynecological examination and ultrasound of female partner was done, and any coexistent female factor was duly noted.

Controlled ovarian stimulation was done using an agonist or antagonist protocol. Gonadotropin dosage was adjusted based on monitoring of follicular size using transvaginal ultrasound after gonadotropin administration of 5-8 days. Human chorionic gonadotropin 10,000 IU IM was given to trigger ovulation when at least 3 or 4 leading follicles reached a mean diameter of 18 mm. Oocytes were retrieved transvaginally 36 hrs after HCG administration.

Oocyte Retrieval And In Vitro Fertilization: All oocyte retrievals were done by transvaginal aspiration under ultrasound guidance 36-37 h after HCG administration. The medium used for flushing the follicles is a flushing medium (Vibro Life). After retrieval, oocytes were rapidly isolated from follicular fluid, rinsed, and placed in a ferti medium (Vibro Life) The evaluation of oocyte maturity was done. Routine preparation was performed by gradient method ICSI was performed in metaphase II oocytes which were then cultured in groups in a 4-well dish at 37°C in the cleavage medium equilibrated with 6% CO₂, 5% O₂, 89% N₂ in a trigas incubator (COOK -MINC Bench Top Incubator).

The present study included two groups: Group A: 500 patients undergoing ART belonged to the conventional culture system of embryo evaluation. Group-B: 500 patients undergoing ART belonged to an uninterrupted culture system of embryo evaluation

Embryo morphology evaluation in group A: After ICSI, injected oocytes are transferred to 4- a well dish kept in groups with 1 well filled with 500µl of clear media kept in a standard benchtop incubator (MINC). Normal diploid fertilization was estimated 16-18 hours after injection on Day-1. Only oocytes with 2 visible pronuclei (2PN) were considered as fertilized & normal and were continued to grow in the same media. The quality of the embryos is assessed by morphological evaluation on Day-2 and Day-3 after injection. Embryo quality was based on the number and the size of blastomeres the degree of fragmentation, and the presence of multinucleated blastomeres.

Embryo morphology evaluation in group B: After ICSI, injected oocytes are transferred to 4- a good

dish kept in groups with 1- well filled with 500 μ l of clear media kept in a standard bench top incubator (MINC) and left undisturbed. On the day of transfer, the quality of the embryos is assessed, and graded accordingly only the top-quality embryos are transferred.

Criteria For Embryo Grading: On Day 2, an embryo was considered as good quality if it had 4 or 5 adequate-sized blastomeres, exhibiting no multinucleation with < 10% cytoplasmic fragmentation. On Day 3, to be considered as good quality the embryos had to have 7 or 8 adequate-sized blastomeres with < 10% cytoplasmic fragmentation and no multinucleation. On Day 4, to be considered of good quality, embryos should exhibit nearly full compaction involving most of the embryo's volume. On Day 5, the most commonly used scoring system for evaluating blastocysts is the one proposed by Gardner and Schoolcraft. Embryos were graded as excellent (Grade 1), good (Grade 2), average (Grade 3), or poor (Grade 4) based on standard morphological criteria for grading cleavage-stage embryos and blastocyst grading on Day 5. Embryo transfer, preferably of top-grade embryos (Grade 1), is usually performed on Day 2 or Day 3 after oocyte pickup (OPU) under ultrasound guidance. The number of embryos transferred depends on the patient's age, the quality of the embryos, previous embryo transfers, and the availability of top-quality embryos. The luteal phase was supported with

intramuscular progesterone, HCG, and LMWH. Serum β -HCG estimation was done on Day 15 after embryo transfer, with values above 50 IU/ml considered positive. Luteal support continued, and a transvaginal ultrasound (TVS) was performed at 6 weeks for all patients. The presence of a fetal pole with cardiac activity is considered a viable (clinical) pregnancy. The luteal support regimen was continued if fetal viability was confirmed, and the pregnancy was considered ongoing if it progressed beyond 12 weeks.

Statistical Analysis: All the available data was refined and uploaded to an MS Excel spreadsheet and analyzed by SPSS version 21 in Windows format. The continuous variables were represented by mean, standard deviations, and percentages. The categorical variables were calculated using the chi-square test for differences between the two groups. The values of p (<0.05) were considered as significant.

Results

In Group A, 69% of respondents are aged 25-35 years, 29.4% are 35-45 years, 6% are under 25, and 0.4% are over 45. In Group B, 71.6% are aged 25-35 years, 18.6% are 35-45 years, 9.6% are under 25, and 0.2% are over 45. The mean age is highest in the 35-45 age group for both groups (Table 1). A chi-square test ($\chi^2 = 5.04$, $p = 0.052$) shows no significant age distribution difference between the groups.

Table 1: Age-wise distribution of cases included in the study

Age Group in years	Group A			Group B		
	Frequency	Percentage	Mean	Frequency	Percentage	Mean
< 25	30	6	23.64	48	9.6	23.75
25 -35	345	69	30.37	358	71.6	30.29
35- 45	123	29.4	38.27	93	38.00	38.00
> 45	2	0.4	46.5	1	0.2	46
Total	500	100		500	100	
Mean			32.004			31.140
P value	0.052					

Table 2 shows that in Group A, 35.8% of the 500 respondents have a male factor problem, 32.4% have a female factor problem, 26.6% fall under the unexplained category, and 5.2% belong to the mixed division. The mean value of infertility causes in Group A is 47.953. In Group B, 35% have a female factor problem, 28.4% have a male factor problem, 22.2% fall under the unexplained

category, and 14.4% belong to the mixed division, with a mean value of 49.036. A chi-square test was applied to determine if there was a significant difference between Group A and Group B regarding infertility causes. The null hypothesis stated no significant difference between the groups. The results are: $\chi^2 = 58.28$, $p = 0.061$.

Table 2: Distribution of cause of infertility

Causes	Group A		Group B		p-value
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	
Female factor	162	32.4	175	35	0.614
Male factor	179	35.8	142	28.4	
Unexplained	133	26.6	111	22.2	
Mixed	26	5.2	72	14.4	
Total	500	100	500	100	

In Group A, out of 500 respondents, 54.2% (271) belong to the 1-5 years group, 29.6% (148) to the 5-10 years group, 11.8% (59) to the above 10 years group, and 4.4% (22) to the below 1-year group. The mean duration of infertility in Group A is 5.211, with the highest category being 1-5 years. In Group B, 52.8% (264) belong to the 1-5 years group, 30.4% (152) to the 5-10 years group, 15.2%

(76) to the above 10 years group, and 1.6% (8) to the below 1-year group. The mean duration of infertility in Group B is 6.093, with the highest category also being 1-5 years. A chi-square test showed that there was no significant difference between the groups, yielding the following results: $\chi^2 = 42.04$, $p = 0.0513$.

Table 3: Distribution of oocyte grading between Group A and Group B cases

Oocyte Grade	Group A		Group B		Total	Percentage
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage		
Average	15	3	46	9.2	61	6.1
Good	482	96.4	441	88.2	923	92.3
Poor	3	0.6	13	2.6	16	1.6
Total	500	100	500	100	1000	100
Mean	49.301		47.619		-	-
P-Value	0.0001*					

*Significant

Table 3 shows the oocyte grading in Group A, 482 out of 500 respondents (96.4%) were under the good grade category, 15 (3%) were in the average grade, and 3 (0.6%) were in the poor grade. The mean oocyte grade for Group A is 49.301. In Group B, 441 respondents (88.2%) had a good grade, 46 (9.2%) in an average grade, and 13 (2.6%) in a poor grade. The mean oocyte grade for Group B is 47.619. A chi-square test results indicate a significant difference ($\chi^2 = 23.825$, $p = 0.001$).

The quality of sperm determination given in Table 4 shows out of the 500 respondents in group A, 474 (94.8%) were in the good grade category, 25 (5%) fell into the average grade category, 1 (0.2%) into the poor grade category, and none (0%); abnormal (ABN) section. Group A sperm count was 49.3. In Group B, 473 (94.6%) were in a good grade, 16 (3.2%) in average grade, 7 (1.4%) in ABN category, and 4 (0.8%) in poor grade Group B sperm grade and 48.95. The p values were 0.013 showing that all quality of sperms in group A was better than group B.

Table 4: Distribution of sperm grading between the two groups

Sperm Grade	Group A		Group B		Total	Percentage
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage		
ABN	0	0	7	1.4	7	0.7
Average	25	5	16	3.2	41	4.1
Good	474	94.8	473	94.6	947	94.7
Poor	1	0.2	4	0.8	5	0.5
Total	500	100	500	100	1000	100
Mean	49.3		48.95			
p-value	0.013*					

*Significant

The fertilization and cleavage rate combined mean value of group A was found to be 85.48 and the mean value for group B was 90.19. The calculated value of the 't' test is 45.48 which is not significant as its p-value is greater than (0.7359). The mean number of embryos in Group A was 6.37, and in Group B, it was 7.66. A Z-test was applied to analyze whether there is a significant difference between Group A and Group B regarding the number of embryos. The mean number of embryos in Group A is 6.37, while in Group B, it is 7.66. The calculated value of the Z-test is 23.568, which is significant since the p-value is less than 0.05 ($0.00234 < 0.05$). The rate of implantation in group A was 326/1351 (24.1%) and in group B was

431/1400 (29.6%). The p values were found to be (0.0015) hence significant.

Table 5 depicts that group A, out of 212 respondents who come under CPR, 151 (71.23%) are in the age group of 25-35 years, 41(19.34%) and 19(8.96%) come under the age group of below 25 years and 1 (0.47%) fall under the age group of above 45 years are in the age group of 35-45 years. In Group B, out of 261 respondents who come under CPR, 199 (76.25%) are in the age group of 25-35 years, 40 (15.33%) are in the age group of 35-45 years, 21 (8.05%) come under the age group of below 25 years and 1 (0.38%) fall under the age group of above 45 years.

Table 5: Outcome of clinical pregnancy in different age groups

Age group	Group A		Group B		P value
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	
< 25	19	8.96	21	8.05	0.931
25 – 35	151	71.23	199	76.25	0.0147*
35 – 45	41	19.34	40	15.33	0.882
Above 45	1	0.47	-	0.38	0.974
Total	212	100.0	261	100.0	-

*Significant

Figure 1 shows that in Group A, out of 212 respondents under CPR, 89 (41.98%) belong to the cause of the malefactor and 18 (8.49%) are in the mixed category. The female factor was the cause in 52(24.53%) and 53 (25%) come under unexplained factor was found in 52 (24.53%) cases. Similarly,

in Group B, out of 261 respondents who come under CPR, 93 (35.63%) were due to female factors, 73(27.97%) were due to male factors and 54(20.69%) were due to unexplained factors. The 'z' test value was 67.64 and the p-value was 0.0361 showing significance.

Figure 1: Distribution of causes of infertility in two groups

Table 6: Implantation rate in transferred embryos of two group

Embryology Parameters	Group A		Group B		Mean	P value
	Embryos	Implantation Rate	Embryos	Implantation Rate		
Grade-1	954	26.6%	1272	32.03%	2.226	0.025*
Grade-2	351	19.6%	111	27.02%	0.462	0.041*
Grade-3	46	17.3%	17	-	0.063	0.794

*Significant

Table 6 shows that there was a significant difference between Group A and Group B regarding Grade I as its p-value is less than 0.05 (0.0253 < 0.05). Similarly, there was a significant difference between Group A and Group B

regarding Grade II as its p-value is less than 0.05 (0.0411 < 0.05). There was no significant difference between Group A and Group B regarding Grade III as its p-value is greater than 0.05 (0.794 > 0.05).

Table 7: Outcome of clinical pregnancy in transferred embryos

Embryology Parameters	Group A		Group B		Mean	P value
	Frequency	CPR	Frequency	CPR		
Grade-1	370	174	458	239	0.828	0.117
Grade-2	114	32	36	16	0.15	0.039*
Grade-3	16	4	6	-	0.022	0.201

*Significant

Table 7 presents data on the outcomes of clinical pregnancies in two groups (A and B) Grade-1: Both Group A and Group B showed a similar frequency of clinical pregnancies (CPR) for Grade-1 embryos,

with no statistically significant difference (p-value = 0.828). Grade-2: Group A had a higher frequency of CPR compared to Group B for Grade-2 embryos. This difference was statistically

significant (p-value = 0.039). Grade-3: While Group A had a higher frequency of CPR for Grade-3 embryos, the difference was not statistically significant (p-value = 0.022). This shows that the embryos with higher embryology grades (Grade-1

and Grade-2) have a greater chance of resulting in clinical pregnancies. However, individual variations and other factors may also influence the outcome.

Table 8: Outcome of clinical pregnancy and Implantation Rate on Day 2 and Day 3

Groups	Day	Frequency	Total Em- bryos	IR	CPR	P value Embryos	P value IR	P value CPR
Group A	Day 2	132	558	19.1	38.66	0.773	0.691	0.001*
Group B	Day 2	116	531	20.3	50.64			
Group A	Day 3	369	793	24.1	48.37	0.0431*	0.002*	0.042*
Group B	Day 3	397	689	32.1	56.72			
Mean		253.5	687.75	23.65	48.6			

*Significant

Table 8 presents data on the outcomes of clinical pregnancy and implantation rates for two groups (A and B) of embryos transferred on day 2 and day 3. Day 2: There were no significant differences in the frequency of embryos transferred, total embryos, implantation rate, or clinical pregnancy rate between Group A and Group B. Day 3: Group B had a significantly higher implantation rate (32.1% vs. 24.1%) and clinical pregnancy rate (56.72% vs.

48.37%) compared to Group A. The implantation rate was significantly higher for embryos transferred on day 3 compared to day 2, suggesting that embryos at the day 3 stage have a better chance of implanting. The clinical pregnancy rate also increased significantly for embryos transferred on day 3, showing that embryos at this stage have a higher likelihood of developing into pregnancies.

Table 9: Total cycle outcome in two groups of cases in the study

	Group A		Group B		P value
	Percentage	Mean	Percentage	Mean	
IR	24.1	9.85	30.7	14.63	0.0364
CPR	37.68	11.01	49.12	16.38	0.0239
Miscarriage Rate	14.88	7.43	11.03	5.18	0.0181
Ongoing Pregnancy rate	23.07	5.146	30.84	8.52	0.0312

Table 9 presents data on the outcomes of clinical pregnancy cycles for two groups (A and B). Group B had a significantly higher implantation rate (30.7%) compared to Group A (24.1%). Group B also had a higher clinical pregnancy rate (49.12%) compared to Group A (37.68%). Similarly, Group A had a slightly higher miscarriage rate (14.88%) compared to Group B (11.03%). Group B had a higher ongoing pregnancy rate (30.84%) compared to Group A (23.07%). The data suggests that Group B had significantly better outcomes in terms of implantation, clinical pregnancy, and ongoing pregnancy rates compared to Group A.

Discussion

Embryo incubation and assessment is a vital step in assisted reproductive technology (ART). Traditionally, embryo assessment has been achieved by Embryo incubation and assessment is a vital step in assisted reproductive removing embryos from a conventional incubator daily for assessment of quality by an embryologist, under a light microscope. Minimal requirements for embryo selection should include standardization, objectivity, minimal harm to the embryo, and a high correlation between embryo quality and

pregnancy rates. As no studies are comparing conventional culture systems and uninterrupted culture systems, most of the studies are comparing the conventional culture and uninterrupted culture with TLEM (uninterrupted culture + morphokinetics). Time-lapse systems (TLSS) have been developed which can take digital images of embryos at frequent time intervals. This allows embryologists, with or without the assistance of computer algorithms, to assess the quality of the embryos without physically removing them from the incubator. Therefore, in our study, we compared the conventional culture system with an uninterrupted culture system to imitate the TLEM by providing an uninterrupted culture system without an embryoscope.

The present study findings suggest that the uninterrupted culture system may offer significant advantages in embryo quality and clinical pregnancy outcomes, as evidenced by the higher number of top-quality embryos, better implantation rates, and improved ongoing pregnancy rates observed in Group B. In our study, the uninterrupted culture system (Group B) demonstrated a statistically significant improvement in the quality of embryos and

implantation rates compared to the conventional culture system (Group A). Specifically, Group B had a higher percentage of top-quality embryos (75% vs. 5%) and a higher implantation rate (30.7% vs. 24.1%). These findings are consistent with previous studies that have suggested that uninterrupted culture systems provide a more stable environment for embryo development, potentially reducing the stress on embryos and improving their viability [7-9].

While the fertilization and cleavage rates were higher in Group B, the difference was not statistically significant, indicating that the uninterrupted culture system does not necessarily affect the early stages of fertilization. However, our findings align with other studies that have reported that uninterrupted culture systems may not significantly impact early embryonic development but could enhance the quality of later-stage embryos [10]. Clinical pregnancy rates and pregnancy rates were significantly higher in group B for both day-3 and day-2 embryo transfers. This is particularly important because it highlights the potential of uninterrupted culture programs to improve overall ART success. The improved results in Group B may be due to the reduced stress and consistent conditions provided by uninterrupted culture programs, as similar studies showing better pregnancy rates in hospitals and the low abortion rates in such programs support [10, 11]. Clinical pregnancy rates and pregnancy rates were significantly higher in group B for both day-3 and day-2 embryo transfers. This is particularly important because it highlights the potential of uninterrupted culture programs to improve overall ART success. The improved results in Group B may be due to the reduced stress and consistent conditions provided by uninterrupted culture programs, as similar studies showing better pregnancy rates in hospitals and the low abortion rates in such programs support. The abortion rate was lower in Group B than in Group A (11.3% vs. 14.8%), suggesting a possible reduction in aneuploidy rates in embryos cultured in an uninterrupted environment. This finding is corroborated by other research indicating that uninterrupted culture systems may decrease the likelihood of chromosomal abnormalities, thereby reducing the risk of miscarriage.

Conclusion

In conclusion, our study supports the growing body of evidence that uninterrupted culture systems can improve embryo quality, implantation rates, and clinical pregnancy outcomes in ART. These findings suggest that the uninterrupted culture system should be considered a viable option for optimizing ART success, potentially leading to better long-term outcomes for patients undergoing fertility treatments.

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